

DEFINING AND NON-DEFINING RELATIVE CLAUSES IN BRITISH ENGLISH GRAMMAR

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Abstract: This article covers the expression of determiners and relative clauses in British English and its context opinion about the place, syntactic and semantic features and their types held. Determinants and their specific characteristics are analyzed. Analyzes tried to prove it based on several examples. A definite article the types of sentences and their participation in the sentence were observed. Linguist different controversial views of scientists about determiners in English have been studied, compared and summarized.

Key words: , Defining , predicate, non-defining, predicativity, secondary particle, British English grammar, quality, determining clauses.

To the grammatical structure or word order of a sentence as each person speaks rather, he pays attention to the short and succinct statement he wants to make. But the order of clauses is important in expressing an idea. Necessary if not, change the parts of the sentence to the meaning of the sentence have a positive or negative effect, as a result, some additional meanings appear in the sentence may appear or spelling, stylistic errors may occur. As the name suggests, non-defining relative clauses tell us more about someone or something, but the information in these clauses does not help us to define what we are talking about. Take for example the sentence: Gorillas, which are large and originate in Africa, can sometimes be found in zoos. In this sentence we are talking about all gorillas, not just some of them. The information in the non-defining relative clause tells us something more about gorillas in general. It does not define a small group of gorillas or an individual gorilla. If the non-defining relative clause were removed from the sentence, the sentence would still be grammatically correct and the meaning would not have changed, although we would have less detail. Non-defining relative clauses are composed of a relative pronoun, a verb, and optional other elements such

as the subject or object of the verb. Commas or parentheses are always used to separate non-defining relative clauses from the rest of the sentence.

We use defining relative clauses to give essential information about someone or something – information that we need in order to understand what or who is being referred to. A defining relative clause usually comes immediately after the noun it describes. We usually use a relative pronoun (e.g. *who*, *that*, *which*, *whose* and *whom*) to introduce a defining relative clause (In the examples, the relative clause is in bold, and the person or thing being referred to is underlined.):

*They're the people **who want to buy our house.***

*Here are some cells **which have been affected.***

*They should give the money to somebody **who they think needs the treatment most.***

English linguists K. N. Kachalova and E. E. Izrayelovichs determine is described as follows: "Opredelenie nazvyvaetsya vtorostepenny chlen predlozheniya, kotoryy oboznachaet priznak predemenda. Opredelenie otnositsya k suschestvitelnomu. Znachitelno reje ono otnositsya k mestoimeniyamsushchestvitelnym" . According to these scholars, the determiner is a noun, indicating the sign of the thing comes connected. But this definition does not fully describe the determiner. Because determiner can indicate not only a thing, but also a person, for example: a funny man Another of the English linguists V. Kaushanskaya to the determiner gives the following definition: "The attribute is a secondary part of the sentence which qualifies a noun, a pronoun, or any other part of speech that has a nominal character. It may be expressed by any part of speech. [17, 252 English grammar writing]. We considered that the scientist was able to fully describe the determiner through this definition. In fact, the determiner can identify nouns and pronouns and any word group is represented by Presently, in many literatures, defining clauses are used is considered as a type of determiner, and the determiner is not only a noun, but also a pronoun it is recognized that it also clarifies the sentences.

CONCLUSION: As a conclusion, after studying a number of literatures, the definition is as follows we gave: The determiner is a syntactic unit and a second-order clause. This syntax What? what kind of? (how?), whose? (whose?), which? (which?),

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how much? (how much?), how many? (how many?) like questions will be answered. Independent words in the sentence, their functional forms, phrases and adverbs (adjective, adjective, adjective phrase, number, pronoun, infinitive, gerund) and primary and secondary clauses and sentences can explain. Determinant explains, the main part - with a definite noun sometimes with pronouns (one, some, any, every, no) is expressed.

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